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Research Article

Socio-Economic Conditions of Silk Handloom Weavers in Azamgarh and Varanasi Districts of Uttar Pradesh

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ABSTRACT

The handloom weaving industry in India employs 14% of the poor (second only to agriculture) and provides around 11% of total textile exports annually. The availability of various fabric patterns and the production of garments and outfits, which are the occupations of millions of weavers employed by the handloom sector in India, have contributed to the rise in popularity of India's handloom industry. The Indian state of Uttar Pradesh has around 130778 handloom weavers. This study discusses the socio-economic conditions of silk handloom weavers in the Azamgarh and Varanasi districts of Uttar Pradesh. The study is based on primary data through a structures interview schedule. The total sample respondents for the survey from Azamgarh and Varanasi were 405, comprising 205 samples from the Azamgarh district and 200 samples from the Varanasi district. In Azamgarh district, 35 representatives were from Akbarpur, 40 samples were from Atraulia, 32 samples were from Jahanagaj, 28 were from Jeeyanpur, and 70 were from Mubarakpur. In the same way, 200 samples were selected from Varanasi, in which 60 samples were from Bajardiha, 50 samples from Jaitpura, 30 samples were from Jallalipura, 30 were from Lohta, and 30 were from Madanpura. The data were evaluated using a simple percentage, annual growth, and compound annual growth rate and presented by pie and bar diagrams. This study is based on location, age, gender, religion, social group, educational qualification, type and size of the family, employment status, type and ownership of dwelling units, ration card, source of loan and purpose of the loan, monthly household income from handloom related activities, and possession of looms. The study results indicated that the position of handloom weavers was miserable. The youth participation in this profession is meagre 3.5 per cent. They are not interested in choosing this as a profession. The majority of workers are men, 91 per cent, and the women worker's participation is not in a good ratio. The Muslim religion dominates the silk handloom weaving industry at 65 per cent. The weaving activity is shared mainly by OBCs 63.1 per cent (Other Backward Class) social group. Most households (63 per cent) have a monthly household income range of less than Rs. 5001-7500, and 56.8 per cent of the respondents have a monthly consumption expenditure of Rs. 5001-7500.

Keywords: Socio-economic condition; Silk handloom weavers; Varanasi district; Uttar Pradesh

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INTRODUCTION

Weaving on handloom is one of the main economic activities in the country, second to agriculture. This weaving industry accounts for around 15 per cent of the total fabric output in the nation and is also responsible for producing over 95 per cent of the world's hand-woven cloth. According to the 4th All India Handloom Census 2019-20, it is estimated that the handloom industry employs 35.23 lakhs workforce directly, and about 28.20 lakhs looms spread all over India. The handloom workers include both handloom weavers and allied workers. The total number of handloom workers is more than 35 lakhs, with which the number of weavers is more than 26 lakhs, and allied workers related to handloom are more than eight lakhs. The export of Indian Handloom products was valued at 370 million USD in 2013 and 223 million USD in 2020-21. The United States ranked as the leading importer of Indian handloom products in 2020-21, followed by the UK, Spain, Italy, Germany and UAE.

The government support for the Indian handloom sector is broadly categorised into two major groups. The National Handloom Development Programme includes the Revival, Reform and Restructuring (RRR) and Comprehensive Handloom Development Scheme. The CHDS has various other sub-components to develop the handloom weaving industry, such as the Cluster Development Programme, Marketing Incentive, Handloom Marketing Assistance, and Development and strengthening of Handloom Institutions.

The significant problems related to handloom weaving are raw materials shortages, lack of credit availability, increased competition from the power loom and mill sector, marketing issues, decentralised unorganised nature of the handloom industry, lack of technological up gradation, poor working conditions, lack of research and training.

In Uttar Pradesh, 1.31 lakh handloom households are engaged in weaving and allied activities, of which 66.7 per cent are located in rural areas and the remaining 33.3 per cent in urban areas. It concluded that the majority of households, i.e. 66.7 per cent, prefer to live in rural areas (4th All India Handloom Census 2019-20). Currently, the handloom weavers in Uttar Pradesh are facing many challenges and striving for their survival due to globalisation, severe competition with power looms, two-faced approaches of government and changing socio-economic conditions. The handloom weaving industry constitutes an everlasting aspect of the rich cultural heritage of India. As an economic activity, the handloom sector occupies a place second only to agriculture in providing livelihood to the people.

Handlooms weaving plays a vital role in uplifting the rural economy in Uttar Pradesh. Traditional items like sarees are produced in the state; the Banarasi saree is the state's most famous product. Varanasi is the largest handloom district, with around 86,438 looms (as per Weavers Service centre, Varanasi). Apart from Varanasi, other districts wherein handloom weaving is practised actively are Azamgarh, Mau, Moradabad, Lucknow, Meerut etc.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Amit Chatterjee and Nehal Jain's (2020) study shows that weaver households in the areas looked at had low living standards and quality of life. It was found that the handloom weavers of Kota Doria live in deplorable social and economic conditions and that different government programmes have been unable to help them make more money.

Ishfaq Majeed et al. (2020), this paper tries to deeply study the social and economic conditions, problems, and challenges of carpet weavers in the Pulwama district of Jammu and Kashmir. The study showed that the situation of carpet weavers is not good because they don't get enough education, have health problems, make low wages, don't get enough help

from the government, and are taken advantage of by the middleman or master weavers.

Gundeti Ramesh (2018) found that the khadi weavers are not getting minimum wages. This paper also found that the Khadi weavers face problems like poor living conditions, high working hours, low wage rates and a lack of social security measures. However, finally, the paper concludes the appropriate policies to uplift the Khadi handloom weavers.

Avoid Roy and Dr Pradeep Chauhan (2017) found that most of the jobs in the industry are done by men with very little education. Weavers face several problems, such as not having enough money to buy new machines, terrible working conditions, a drop in wages, an increase in the price of yarn, a lack of government support, a lack of domestic demand and market, and so on. Plans aren't carried out well, and not all the money and facilities get to the people who need them. So it's essential to plan and implement those plans so that people in the area can use those facilities well.

Dr B Sadanandam's (2016) study looks at the weavers' social and economic situation and comes up with ways to help them. This study is based on primary data that was gathered through interviews with 57 active societies in the Telangana State district of Warangal. The study showed that weavers face several problems: lack of money, inability to buy modern machines, terrible working conditions, low pay, and lack of government support.

Gulati S (2016) study was about the Geographical Indication (GI) certificate for Banarasi silk products, which fall into four categories: silk embroidery, textile goods, silk brocades, silk saris, and dress material. Geographical Indication (GI) certification is different because nothing is made outside of six districts in Uttar Pradesh: Varanasi, Azamgarh, Chandauli, Jaunpur, Mirzapur, and Sant Ravi Das Nagar (Bhadohi).

Ansari M. Shoaib's (2016) study was about the different kinds of information that weavers need, such as information about raw materials, capital, trends, and intellectual property rights (IPR).

Shaw Tanusree (2015) found that India's industrialisation has hurt the handloom weavers of Varanasi. Some reasons for the decline of the handloom industry in Varanasi are the rise of capitalist production, the invention of power looms, the rising cost of yarn, low wages, and problems with finding workers. Weavers are also in bad conditions because they can't get credit and are too far into debt to keep their businesses going. She also suggested that policymakers give the money needed to help handloom weavers.

Dr G. Prathap and Prof. M. Chinnaswamy Naidu (2015) found that there are 54 men, 90%, and only six women, 10%. Also, 48 people are married, which is 80%, and 12 people are not married, which is 20%. Most people who weave by hand are happy to live in a joint family. The handloom weavers don't make enough money to live well. Most of the people who answered know about the health insurance scheme.

S. Tasneem and M. Abdul (2014), the study shows the main things that made women work in handlooms were economic need, unemployment, poverty, low income, inability to read or write, and having a big family. Due to economic and political factors, the handloom weaving industry in Mubarakpur town has been slowly decreasing for the last few decades. These factors have hurt the situation of female weavers. So, the government should deal with problems related to women working and come up with a plan to help poor female weavers. He also suggested things that could be done to fix these dire situations. He said that the government take steps to improve the education system, give the weavers cheaper raw materials, make sure they always have enough electricity, and open more government hospitals in the district.

G. Naga Raju and K. Viyyanna Rao (2014) explained that the handloom industry is crucial to preserving the country's heritage and culture. It is also an essential part of the country's economy. In 2011-12, the handloom sector produced 6900 million square metres, which was about 25% more than the 5493 million square metres made in 2003-04. Regarding jobs, the handloom sector is only second to agriculture in economic activity. With 23.77 million handlooms, the industry employs 43.31 million people, of which 77.9% are women and 28% are from Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. The handloom sector makes up about 15% of all the cloth made in the country. It also helps the country earn money from exports since 95% of all hand-woven fabric in the world comes from India. But this sector has problems like old technology, a disorganised production system, low productivity, insufficient working capital, a limited range of products, and weak marketing links. Also, the handloom sector has never been able to compete well with the power loom sector or the mill sector.

Tawheed Yousuf et al (2013) this study, we looked at the socio-economic background and problems of silk weavers in Srinagar city and tried to come up with suggestions for how to deal with the grey areas. The study's results showed that the weavers were in a bad situation. They were weak because they couldn't read or write, didn't have enough money, had health problems, were paid very little, and didn't get much help from the government.

Beddig C. (2008) focused on the Varanasi cluster, where men mostly do weaving, and the number of weavers is thought to have grown by three times in the last 34 years. The government says that 59 per cent of the weavers can read and write. Most people who weave in the Varanasi district live in cities and work in certain parts of the cities. 90% of weavers in cities are Muslims, but only 30% of weavers in villages are Muslims. The other 70% are primarily low-caste Hindus. Sattiwalas act as middlemen between weavers and traders. They usually get a 3 per cent

commission and don't do the craft themselves. Grihastha buys from weavers or master weavers and sells to Gaddedars, who take on the risk of the transaction. Gaddedars are large merchants who may hire weavers on a wage or piece-rate basis. They only do wholesale business and also sell yarn. It is thought that there are between 100 and 300 designers and between 300 and 500.

THE OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To study the socio-economic conditions of handloom weavers in Azamgarh and Varanasi districts of Uttar Pradesh.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design was adopted to conduct the study. The researcher attempted to identify the existing socio-economic conditions of handloom weavers in the Azamgarh and Varanasi districts of Uttar Pradesh. The study is based on primary data through a structured interview schedule. The total sample respondents for the survey from Azamgarh and Varanasi were 405, comprising 205 samples from the Azamgarh district and 200 samples from the Varanasi district. In Azamgarh district, 35 representatives were from Akbarpur, 40 samples were from Atraulia, 32 samples were from Jahanagaj, 28 were from Jeeyanpur, and 70 were from Mubarakpur. In the same way, 200 samples were selected from Varanasi, in which 60 samples were from Bajardiha, 50 samples from Jaitpura, 30 samples were from Jallalipura, 30 were from Lohta, and 30 were from Madanpura. Total samples of 405 of which 90 respondents working as independent were selected randomly, 272 respondents working under master weaver were selected randomly, 20 master weavers were purposively selected for the study and 23 respondents working under cooperative society were purposively selected for the study. The data was evaluated using a simple percentage, annual growth, compound annual growth rate and presented by pie and bar diagram.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This paper seeks to analyse and present the socio-economic conditions of the handloom weavers living in the Varanasi and Azamgarh districts of Uttar Pradesh in, India.

This study examines the following key areas: Age, gender, social grouping and religion, level of

education, marital status, type of houses, ownership of houses, types of family and nature of family, types of ration cards, earlier occupation, type of employment status, health condition, monthly household income from weaving activities, monthly household income from all sources, monthly household consumption expenditure, sources of loan and purpose of loan and type of employment status.

Table: 1 Distribution of respondents by Age Group

Districts/Age Group	Up to 25 Years	26-35 Years	36-45 Years	46-55 Years	56-65 Years	Above 60 Years	Total
Azamgarh	7 (3.4)	45 (22.0)	67 (32.7)	65 (31.7)	17 (8.3)	4 (2.0)	205 (100)
Akbarpur	1 (2.9)	7 (20.0)	14 (40.0)	9 (25.7)	2 (5.7)	2 (5.7)	35 (100)
Atraulia	1 (2.5)	10 (25.0)	12 (30.0)	13 (32.5)	3 (7.5)	1 (2.5)	40 (100)
Jahanaganj		7 (0.0)	9 (28.1)	12 (37.5)	4 (12.5)		32 (100)
Jeeyanpur		7 (0.0)	7 (25.0)	12 (42.9)	2 (7.1)		28 (100)
Mubarakpur	5 (7.1)	14 (20.0)	25 (35.7)	19 (27.1)	6 (8.6)	1 (1.4)	70 (100)
Varanasi	7 (3.5)	42 (21.0)	82 (41.0)	54 (27.0)	11 (5.5)	4 (2.0)	200 (100)
Bajardiha	1 (1.7)	13 (21.7)	26 (43.3)	15 (25.0)	4 (6.7)	1 (1.7)	60 (100)
Jaitpura	2 (4.0)	13 (26.0)	17 (34.0)	14 (28.0)	2 (4.0)	2 (4.0)	50 (100)
Jalalipura	1 (3.3)	4 (13.3)	15 (50.0)	7 (23.3)	3 (10.0)		30 (100)
Lohta		8 (0.0)	12 (26.7)	8 (40.0)	1 (26.7)	1 (3.3)	30 (100)
Madanpura	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	12 (40.0)	10 (33.3)	1 (3.3)		30 (100)
Grand Total	14 (3.5)	87 (21.5)	149 (36.8)	119 (29.4)	28 (6.9)	8 (2.0)	405 (100)

Source: compiled from collected data. Note: Figures in parentheses are the percentage of the responden

The age of the respondents and their respective percentages are presented in the table: 1. In Azamgarh district, out of 205 respondents, 67 respondents (33 per cent) are in the age group of 36-45 years, 65 respondents (32 per cent) are in the age group of 46-55 years, 45 respondents (22 per cent) are in the age group of 26-35 years, 17 respondents (8.3 per cent) are in the age group of 56-65 years, 7 respondents (3.4 per cent) are in the age group of up to 25 years, and the rest four respondents (2 per cent) are in the age group of above 65 years.

In the same way in the table 5.1, the Varanasi district has 200 respondents, 82 respondents (41 percent) are in the age group of 36-45 years, 54 respondents (27 percent) are in the age group of 46-55 years, 42

respondents (21 percent) are in the age group of 26-35 years, 11 respondents (5.5 percent) are in the age group of 56-65 years, 7 (3.5 percent) respondents are in the age group of up to 25 years and the rest 4 respondents (2 percent) are in the age group of above 65 years.

It is found that majority of the respondents (36.8 %) were between 36-45 years of age group. Nearly (29.4 %) of weavers in the survey belonged to 46-55 years of age group. The age group of the handloom weavers in Varanasi and Azamgarh districts shows that the number of respondents up to 25 years of age is low. It is observed that the younger generation is not opting weaving as their preferred profession

Table: 2 Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Districts/Gender	Male	Female	Total
Azamgarh	186 (91)	19 (9)	205 (100)
Akbarpur	31 (89)	4 (11)	35 (100)
Jahanaganj	29 (91)	3 (9)	32 (100)
Jeeyanpur	26 (93)	2 (7)	28 (100)
Mubarakpur	62 (89)	8 (11)	70 (100)
Varanasi	182 (91)	18 (9)	200 (100)
Bajardiha	55 (92)	5 (8)	60 (100)
Jaitpura	46 (92)	4 (8)	50 (100)
Jalalipura	27 (90)	3 (10)	30 (100)
Lohta	27 (90)	3 (10)	30 (100)
Madanpura	27 (90)	3 (10)	30 (100)
Total	368 (91)	37 (9)	405 (100)

Source: Compiled from collected data

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

The Table: 2 explains the gender of the respondents in Azamgarh district and out of 205 respondents 186 (91 percent) of respondents are men and 9 (19 percent) of the respondents are women. On the other hand in Varanasi district, out of 200 respondents 182 (91 percent) of the respondents are men and the rest 18 (9 percent) of the respondents are women.

It is found that nearly 91 percent of weavers were male while only 9 percent were female. It is observed that male handloom weavers are assisted by the female

members of their family. Therefore, in the study area there is a direct employment of male handloom weavers towards handloom weaving rather than female members.

Table: 3 Social Group of Respondents

District/Social Group	SCs	STs	OBCs	Others	Total
Azamgarh	34 (16.6)	4 (2.0)	162 (79.0)	5 (2.4)	205 (100)
Akbarpur	7 (20.0)	1 (2.9)	27 (77.1)		35 (100)
Atraulia	10 (25.0)		26 (65.0)	4 (10.0)	40 (100)
Jahanaganj	5 (15.6)		27 (84.4)		32 (100)
Jeeyanpur	2 (7.1)	1 (3.6)	25 (89.3)		28 (100)
Mubarakpur	10 (14.3)	2 (2.9)	57 (81.4)	1 (1.4)	70 (100)
Varanasi	46 (23.0)	4 (2.0)	134 (67.0)	16 (8.0)	200 (100)
Bajardiha	14 (23.3)	1 (1.7)	43 (71.7)	2 (3.3)	60 (100)
Jaitpura	11 (22.0)	2 (4.0)	33 (66.0)	4 (8.0)	50 (100)
Jalalipura	4 (13.3)	1 (3.3)	22 (73.3)	3 (10.0)	30 (100)
Lohta	5 (16.7)		20 (66.7)	5 (16.7)	30 (100)
Madanpura	12 (40.0)		16 (53.3)	2 (6.7)	30 (100)
Grand Total	80 (19.8)	8 (2.0)	296 (73.1)	21 (5.2)	405 (100)

Source: Compiled from collected data

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

The given table: 3 explains the social group and out of 205 respondents in Azamgarh district four social groups are engaging in handloom weaving activity. Among the four social groups 79 percent (162) of respondents belong to OBCs (Other Backward Class) 16.6 percent (34) respondents are SCs (Scheduled Castes) 2.4 percent (5) respondents are Others and 2 percent (4) respondents are found from STs

(Scheduled Tribes). Majority of respondents are from OBCs who is engaged in the weaving activity.

On the other hand in Varanasi district out of 200 respondents 67percent (134) respondents are from the OBCs (Other Backward Class) social group, 23 percent (46) respondents belong to SCs (Scheduled Castes) social group and 8 percent (16) respondents are from the Others social group and lowest from STs

(Scheduled Tribes) who recorded 2 percent (4) in numbers.

whereas 19.8 per cent of respondents were from SCs social group.

It is found that most of the respondents i.e. 73.1 per cent of respondents belonged to OBCs social group

Table: 4 Religion of the Respondents

District/Cluster	Hindu	Muslim	Total
Azamgarh	61 (30)	144 (70)	205 (100)
Akbarpur	13 (37)	22 (63)	35 (100)
Atraulia	17 (43)	23 (58)	40 (100)
Jahanaganj	6 (19)	26 (81)	32 (100)
Jeeyanpur	5 (18)	23 (82)	28 (100)
Mubarakpur	20 (29)	50 (71)	70 (100)
Varanasi	82 (41)	118 (59)	200 (100)
Bajardiha	23 (38)	37 (62)	60 (100)
Jaitpura	24 (48)	26 (52)	50 (100)
Jalalipura	8 (27)	22 (73)	30 (100)
Lohta	9 (30)	21 (70)	30 (100)
Madanpura	18 (60)	12 (40)	30 (100)
Grand Total	143 (35)	262 (65)	405 (100)

Source: Compiled from collected data

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

The table 5.4 presents religion wise distribution of respondents. In Azamgarh district out of 205

respondents 144 (70 percent) respondents are Muslim, 61 (30 percent) respondents are Hindu.

In Varanasi district, out of 200 respondents 118 (59 percent) respondents belong to Muslim religion and 82 (41 percent) respondents are Hindu.

In the study area it is found that majority (65 percent) of the weavers belonged to Muslim religion and (35 percent) of the weavers were from Hindu religion.

Table: 5 Marital Status of Respondents

District/Marital Status	Married	Un-Married	Widowed/Widower	Divorced/Separated	Total
Azamgarh	172 (83.9)	24 (11.7)	8 (3.9)	1 (0.5)	205 (100)
Akbarpur	33 (94.3)	1 (2.9)	1 (2.9)	0 (0.0)	35 (100)
Atraulia	29 (72.5)	10 (25.0)	1 (2.5)	0 (0.0)	40 (100)
Jahanaganj	29 (90.6)	1 (3.1)	2 (6.3)	0 (0.0)	32 (100)
Jeeyanpur	25 (89.3)	2 (7.1)	1 (3.6)	0 (0.0)	28 (100)
Mubarakpur	56 (80.0)	10 (14.3)	3 (4.3)	1 (1.4)	70 (100)
Varanasi	170 (85.0)	20 (10.0)	9 (4.5)	1 (0.5)	200 (100)
Bajardiha	52 (86.7)	5 (8.3)	3 (5.0)	0 (0.0)	60 (100)
Jaitpura	39 (78.0)	9 (18.0)	2 (4.0)	0 (0.0)	50 (100)
Jalalipura	25 (83.3)	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	1 (3.3)	30 (100)
Lohta	27 (90.0)	1 (3.3)	2 (6.7)	0 (0.0)	30 (100)
Madanpura	27 (90.0)	3 (10.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	30 (100)
Grand Total	342 (84.4)	44 (10.9)	17 (4.2)	2 (0.5)	405 (100)

Source: Compiled from collected data

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

The table: 5 explains the marital status of respondents in Azamgarh and Varanasi districts. In Azamgarh district out of 205 respondents, 172 (83.9 percent) respondents are married and 24 (11.7 percent) respondents are un-married and very few which is insignificant proportion 13.9 percent and 0.5 percent

are widowed/widower and divorced/separated respectively.

In Varanasi district large proportion 170 (85 percent) respondents reported from married, 20 (10 percent) respondents are un-married, while 9 (4.5 percent)

respondents are widowed/widower and very few 1 (0.5 percent) respondents are reported from divorced/separated category.

followed by un-married (10.9 percent), widowed or widower (4.2 percent) and divorced or separated (0.5 percent).

It is concluded that in both districts higher percentage of weavers are married (84.4 percent)

Table: 6 Distribution of Respondents by Type of Family

District/Type of Family	Joint	Nuclear	Total
Azamgarh	90	115	205
	(43.9)	(56.1)	(100.0)
Akbarpur	14	21	35
	(40.0)	(60.0)	(100.0)
Atraulia	16	24	40
	(40.0)	(60.0)	(100.0)
Jahanaganj	14	18	32
	(43.8)	(56.3)	(100.0)
Jeeyanpur	13	15	28
	(46.4)	(53.6)	(100.0)
Mubarakpur	33	37	70
	(47.1)	(52.9)	(100.0)
Varanasi	86	114	200
	(43.0)	(57.0)	(100.0)
Bajardiha	27	33	60
	(45.0)	(55.0)	(100.0)
Jaitpura	20	30	50
	(40.0)	(60.0)	(100.0)
Jalalipura	15	15	30
	(50.0)	(50.0)	(100.0)
Lohta	11	19	30
	(36.7)	(63.3)	(100.0)
Madanpura	13	17	30
	(43.3)	(56.7)	(100.0)
Grand Total	176	229	405
	(43.5)	(56.5)	(100.0)

Source: Compiled from collected data

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

In Azamgarh district, out of 205 respondents 115 (56.1 percent) respondents are living in nuclear families and 90 (43.9 percent) respondents are living in joint families.

In Varanasi district the same trend is also been observed. Out of 200 respondents 114 (57 percent)

respondents are living in nuclear families and 86 (43 percent) respondents are living in joint families.

It is concluded that majority of the respondents (56.5%) have joint family and 43.5% of respondents have nuclear family.

Table: 7 Distribution of Respondents by Type of House

Districts/Type of House	Kutchha	Semi-Pucca	Pucca	Total
Azamgarh	47	71	87	205
	(22.9)	(34.6)	(42.4)	(100.0)
Akbarpur	14	8	13	35
	(40.0)	(22.9)	(37.1)	(100.0)
Atraulia	4	18	18	40
	(10.0)	(45.0)	(45.0)	(100.0)
Jahanaganj	7	19	6	32
	(21.9)	(59.4)	(18.8)	(100.0)
Jeeyanpur	11	5	12	28
	(39.3)	(17.9)	(42.9)	(100.0)
Mubarakpur	11	21	38	70
	(15.7)	(30.0)	(54.3)	(100.0)
Varanasi	3	39	158	200
	(1.5)	(19.5)	(79.0)	(100.0)
Bajardiha	0	10	50	60
	(0.0)	(16.7)	(83.3)	(100.0)
Jaitpura	0	12	38	50
	(0.0)	(24.0)	(76.0)	(100.0)
Jalalipura	0	7	23	30
	(0.0)	(23.3)	(76.7)	(100.0)
Lohta	3	6	21	30
	(10.0)	(20.0)	(70.0)	(100.0)
Madanpura	0	4	26	30
	(0.0)	(13.3)	(86.7)	(100.0)
Grand Total	50	110	245	405
	(12.3)	(27.2)	(60.5)	(100.0)

Source: Compiled from collected data

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

Table: 7 explains the types of houses they are living. In Azamgarh district, out of 205 respondents 87 (42.4

percent) respondents are living in pucca houses, 71 (34.6 percent) respondent are living in semi-pucca

houses and 47 (22.9 percent) respondents are living in kutcha houses. In Varanasi district, out of 200 respondents 158 (79 percent) respondents are living in pucca houses, 39 (19.5 percent) respondents are living in semi-pucca houses and lowest 3 (1.5 percent) respondents are living in kutcha houses.

It is found that majority of respondents 245 (60.5 percent) are living in pucca houses, rest 27.2 percent and 12.3 percent are living in semi-pucca and kutcha houses respectively.

Table: 8 Distribution of Respondents by Ownership of House

District/Ownership of Dwelling	Own	Rented	Total
Azamgarh	192 (94)	13 (6)	205 (100)
Akbarpur	33 (94)	2 (6)	35 (100)
Atraulia	36 (90)	4 (10)	40 (100)
Jahanaganj	31 (97)	1 (3)	32 (100)
Jeeyanpur	28 (100)	0 (0)	28 (100)
Mubarakpur	64 (91)	6 (9)	70 (100)
Varanasi	172 (86)	28 (14)	200 (100)
Bajardiha	49 (82)	11 (18)	60 (100)
Jaitpura	47 (94)	3 (6)	50 (100)
Jalalipura	26 (87)	4 (13)	30 (100)
Lohta	26 (87)	4 (13)	30 (100)
Madanpura	24 (80)	6 (20)	30 (100)
Grand Total	364 (90)	41 (10)	405 (100)

Source: Compiled from collected data

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

Table: 8 reveals in Azamgarh district, out of 205 respondents, 192 (94 percent) respondents are living in owned houses and 13 (6 percent) of respondents are living in rented houses. The respondents who continue their work under their own is quite better in terms of socio economic status as well they possess own houses. In Varanasi district, 172 (86 percent) of

respondents living in owned houses and 28 (14 percent) of respondents are living in rented houses. It is found that majority of respondents 364 (90 %) were the owner of their house and rest of them (10 %) were living in rented house.

Table: 9 Distribution of Respondents by Educational Qualification

Districts/Education	Never Attended School	Below Primary	Primary	Middle	High School	Higher Secondary	Graduate and Above	Total
Azamgarh	56 (27.3)	65 (31.7)	60 (29.3)	19 (9.3)	4 (2.0)	1 (0.5)	0 (0.0)	205 (100.0)
Akbarpur	9 (25.7)	10 (28.6)	13 (37.1)	2 (5.7)	1 (2.9)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	35 (100.0)
Atraulia	4 (10.0)	10 (25.0)	18 (45.0)	7 (17.5)	1 (2.5)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	40 (100.0)
Jahanaganj	16 (50.0)	9 (28.1)	7 (21.9)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	32 (100.0)
Jeeyanpur	12 (42.9)	13 (46.4)	3 (10.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	28 (100.0)
Mubarakpur	15 (21.4)	23 (32.9)	19 (27.1)	10 (14.3)	2 (2.9)	1 (1.4)	0 (0.0)	70 (100.0)
Varanasi	44 (22.0)	49 (24.5)	56 (28.0)	28 (14.0)	16 (8.0)	5 (2.5)	2 (1.0)	200 (100.0)
Bajardiha	12 (20.0)	20 (33.3)	16 (26.7)	8 (13.3)	2 (3.3)	2 (3.3)	0 (0.0)	60 (100.0)
Jaitpura	16 (32.0)	13 (26.0)	14 (28.0)	6 (12.0)	1 (2.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	50 (100.0)
Jalalipura	10 (33.3)	6 (20.0)	7 (23.3)	3 (10.0)	2 (6.7)	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	30 (100.0)
Lohta	3 (10.0)	8 (26.7)	9 (30.0)	5 (16.7)	5 (16.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	30 (100.0)
Madanpura	3 (10.0)	2 (6.7)	10 (33.3)	6 (20.0)	6 (20.0)	2 (6.7)	1 (3.3)	30 (100.0)
Grand Total	100 (24.7)	114 (28.1)	116 (28.6)	47 (11.6)	20 (4.9)	6 (1.5)	2 (0.5)	405 (100.0)

Source: Compiled from collected data Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

In the table: 9, in Azamgarh district, out of 205 respondents, 65 (31.7 percent) of respondents have below primary level education, 60 (29.3 percent) of respondents are primary level education, 56 (27.3 percent) of respondents have never attended, 19 (9.3 percent) of respondents have middle level of education and 4 (2 percent) of respondents have high school, and very few in higher secondary, graduation and above levels of education.

In Varanasi district, out of 200 respondents (22 percent) 44 respondents are never attended school, 49 (24.5 percent) respondents have below primary level education, 56 (28 percent) respondents have primary level of education, 28 (14 percent) respondents have

middle level education, 16 (8 percent) of the respondents in the category of high school, 5 (2.5 percent) respondents in higher secondary and lowest 2 (1 percent) respondents have in the category of graduate and above level of education.

It is found that majority of respondents (28.6 %) were primary level of education and about 28.1% respondents have below primary level of education and 24.7 % respondents have never attended school. It is observed that less educated respondents are opting for handloom weaving in larger number because handloom weavers prefer their traditional occupation immediately rather than qualifying further.

Table: 10 Distribution of Respondents by Earlier Occupation

District/Earlier Occupation	Weaving	Agriculture	Government Employee	Private Employee	Total
Azamgarh	167 (81.5)	30 (14.6)	1 (0.5)	7 (3.4)	205 (100)
Akbarpur	28 (80.0)	6 (17.1)	1 (2.9)	0 (0.0)	35 (100)
Atraulia	35 (87.5)	3 (7.5)	0 (0.0)	2 (5.0)	40 (100)
Jahanaganj	25 (78.1)	7 (21.9)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	32 (100)
Jeeyanpur	22 (78.6)	4 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	2 (7.1)	28 (100)
Mubarakpur	57 (81.4)	10 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	3 (4.3)	70 (100)
Varanasi	164 (82.0)	27 (13.5)	3 (1.5)	6 (3.0)	200 (100)
Bajardiha	51 (85.0)	6 (10.0)	1 (1.7)	2 (3.3)	60 (100)
Jaitpura	41 (82.0)	7 (14.0)	1 (2.0)	1 (2.0)	50 (100)
Jalalipura	24 (80.0)	6 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	30 (100)
Lohta	23 (76.7)	5 (16.7)	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	30 (100)
Madanpura	25 (83.3)	3 (10.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (6.7)	30 (100)
Grand Total	331 (81.7)	57 (14.1)	4 (1.0)	13 (3.2)	405 (100)

Source: Compiled from collected data

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

The table: 10 explains the earlier occupation of respondents before entering to the weaving occupation. In Azamgarh district large proportion of the sample respondents were continuing with the weaving prior to turning main occupation. Out of (205) respondents 167 (81.5 percent) respondents have earlier occupation as weaving, 30 (14.6 percent) respondents have come to this occupation from

agriculture, 7 (3.4 percent) respondents have entered this occupation from private employee, 1 (0.5 percent) respondents have chosen this occupation from government employee.

In Varanasi district similar results were found from this district also. The respondents do not want to be side-lined from their traditional bread earning

occupation hence adhered to the profession. Out of 200 respondents 167 (81.5 percent) respondents have weaving as an earlier occupation. It says that their career has started with weaving occupation. They have adopted it as a tradition or heredity, 30 (14.6 percent) respondents have earlier occupation is agriculture, 7 (3.4 percent) respondents have from private employee, 1 (0.5 percent) respondents have from government employee.

It is concluded from the study that majority of the respondents i.e. 81.7 percent from the weaving background. It is also noteworthy to mention that very small proportion of the people entered this occupation outside the weaving line i.e. 14.1 percent from agriculture background, 3.2 percent from private employee and 1 percent respondents from government employee.

Table: II Health Condition of Respondents

District/Health Condition	Hearing	Back Pain	Joint Pain	Eye Sight	Blood Pressure	Total
Azamgarh	21 (10.2)	40 (19.5)	36 (17.6)	105 (51.2)	3 (1.5)	205 (100)
Akbarpur	6 (17.1)	7 (20.0)	5 (14.3)	17 (48.6)	0 (0.0)	35 (100)
Atraulia	7 (17.5)	8 (20.0)	7 (17.5)	16 (40.0)	2 (5.0)	40 (100)
Jahanaganj	1 (3.1)	5 (15.6)	7 (21.9)	19 (59.4)	0 (0.0)	32 (100)
Jeeyanpur	0 (0.0)	4 (14.3)	5 (17.9)	19 (67.9)	0 (0.0)	28 (100)
Mubarakpur	7 (10.0)	16 (22.9)	12 (17.1)	34 (48.6)	1 (1.4)	70 (100)
Varanasi	49 (24.5)	47 (23.5)	44 (22.0)	58 (29.0)	2 (1.0)	200 (100)
Bajardiha	13 (21.7)	17 (28.3)	14 (23.3)	16 (26.7)	0 (0.0)	60 (100)
Jaitpura	12 (24.0)	9 (18.0)	8 (16.0)	19 (38.0)	2 (4.0)	50 (100)
Jalalipura	9 (30.0)	6 (20.0)	7 (23.3)	8 (26.7)	0 (0.0)	30 (100)
Lohta	10 (33.3)	7 (23.3)	7 (23.3)	6 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	30 (100)
Madanpura	5 (16.7)	8 (26.7)	8 (26.7)	9 (30.0)	0 (0.0)	30 (100)
Grand Total	70 (17.3)	87 (21.5)	80 (19.8)	163 (40.2)	5 (1.2)	405 (100)

Source: Compiled from collected data.

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondent

In the table: 11, in Azamgarh district, out of 205 respondents, 105 (51.2 percent) of respondents have eye sight problem, 40 (19.5 percent) of respondents are suffer from back pain, 36 (17.6 percent) of respondents have problem of joint pain, 21 (10.2 percent) of respondents have problem of hearing and 3 (1.5 percent) of respondents have problem of high blood pressure.

In Varanasi district, out of 200 respondents, 58 (29 percent) of respondents have eye sight problem, 47 (23.5 percent) of respondents are suffer from back pain, 44 (22 percent) of respondents have problem of

joint pain, 49 (24.5 percent) of respondents have problem of hearing and 2 (1 percent) of respondents have problem of high blood pressure.

It is found that majority of respondents 163 (40.2 %) have eye sight problem, 87 (21.5 percent) of respondents are suffer from back pain, 80 (19.8 percent) of respondents have problem of joint pain, 70 (17.3 percent) of respondents have problem of hearing and 5 (1.2 percent) of respondents have problem of high blood pressure.

Table: 12 Monthly Household Income of the Respondents from handloom weaving activities:

Districts/ Household Income	2500-5000	5001-7500	7501-10000	10001-15000	15001-20000	Total
Azamgarh	18 (8.8)	152 (74.1)	35 (17.1)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	205 (100)
Akbarpur	5 (14.3)	24 (68.6)	6 (17.1)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	35 (100)
Atraulia	3 (7.5)	30 (75.0)	7 (17.5)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	40 (100)
Jahanaganj	4 (12.5)	28 (87.5)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	32 (100)
Jeeyanpur	6 (21.4)	21 (75.0)	1 (3.6)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	28 (100)
Mubarakpur	0 (0.0)	49 (70.0)	21 (30.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	70 (100)
Varanasi	6 (3.0)	104 (52.0)	60 (30.0)	28 (14.0)	2 (1.0)	200 (100)
Bajardiha	2 (3.3)	31 (51.7)	19 (31.7)	8 (13.3)	0 (0.0)	60 (100)
Jaitpura	1 (2.0)	26 (52.0)	14 (28.0)	7 (14.0)	2 (4.0)	50 (100)
Jalalipura	0 (0.0)	16 (53.3)	9 (30.0)	5 (16.7)	0 (0.0)	30 (100)
Lohta	3 (10.0)	14 (46.7)	9 (30.0)	4 (13.3)	0 (0.0)	30 (100)
Madanpura	0 (0.0)	17 (56.7)	9 (30.0)	4 (13.3)	0 (0.0)	30 (100)
Grand Total	24 (5.9)	256 (63.2)	95 (23.5)	28 (6.9)	2 (0.5)	405 (100)

Source: Compiled from collected data.

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

The table: 12 reveals the range of monthly household income of the respondents in Azamgarh district in which (74.1) percent i.e. 152 respondents fall in the income group of Rs. 5001-7500, (17.1) percent i.e. 35 respondents have income group of Rs. 7500-10000, (8.8) percent i.e. 18 respondents have income group of Rs. 2500-5000, and no respondent have found in

monthly income groups of Rs. 15001 – 20000 and Rs. 20001- 25000.

On the other hand, in Varanasi district, out of 200 respondents (52) percent i.e. 104 respondents fall in the income group of Rs. 5001-7500, (30) percent i.e. 60 respondents have income group of Rs. 7501-10000, (14) percent i.e. 28 respondents have income group of Rs. 10001-15000, (3) percent i.e. 6 respondents have

monthly income group of Rs. 2500-5000 and last (1) percent 2 respondents has monthly income group of Rs. 15001-20000.

It is found that the majority of the respondents (63.2 percent) in both the districts have the monthly household income which is between Rs. 5001 to 7500. Finally the respondents in Varanasi district has monthly household income is better than the

respondents in the Azamgarh district, because the designs made by the Varanasi weavers are relatively innovative (particularly jacquard) and with modern technology. It is also observed that at present handloom weaving is struggling with financial conditions and not even enable the handloom weavers to satisfy their essential needs for life. So the weavers in the study area depends on other sources to fulfil the basic requirements.

Table: 13 Monthly Consumption Expenditure of Household

Districts/Monthly Consumption Expenditure of Household	2500-5000	5001-7500	7501-10000	10000-15000	15000-20000	Total
Azamgarh	34 (16.6)	136 (66.3)	27 (13.2)	5 (2.4)	3 (1.5)	205 (100.0)
Akbarpur	6 (17.1)	24 (68.6)	5 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	35 (100.0)
Atraulia	3 (7.5)	28 (70.0)	7 (17.5)	0 (0.0)	2 (5.0)	40 (100.0)
Jahanaganj	4 (12.5)	28 (87.5)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	32 (100.0)
Jeeyanpur	6 (21.4)	20 (71.4)	2 (7.1)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	28 (100.0)
Mubarakpur	15 (21.4)	36 (51.4)	13 (18.6)	5 (7.1)	1 (1.4)	70 (100.0)
Varanasi	7 (3.5)	94 (47.0)	72 (36.0)	23 (11.5)	4 (2.0)	200 (100.0)
Bajardiha	4 (6.7)	27 (45.0)	22 (36.7)	6 (10.0)	1 (1.7)	60 (100.0)
Jaitpura	0 (0.0)	22 (44.0)	19 (38.0)	9 (18.0)	0 (0.0)	50 (100.0)
Jalalipura	0 (0.0)	17 (56.7)	12 (40.0)	1 (3.3)	0 (0.0)	30 (100.0)
Lohta	3 (10.0)	13 (43.3)	9 (30.0)	5 (16.7)	0 (0.0)	30 (100.0)
Madanpura	0 (0.0)	15 (50.0)	10 (33.3)	2 (6.7)	3 (10.0)	30 (100.0)
Grand Total	41 (10.1)	230 (56.8)	99 (24.4)	28 (6.9)	7 (1.7)	405 (100.0)

Source: Compiled from collected data. Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondent

Table: 13 explains the monthly household expenditure on food and non-food items. In Azamgarh district out of 205 respondents, 136 (66.3 percent) of respondents have the monthly household consumption expenditure of Rs. 5001-7500, 34 (16.6 percent) of respondents have the monthly household consumption expenditure of Rs. 2500-5000, 27 (13.2 percent) of respondents have the monthly household consumption expenditure of Rs. 7501-10,000, 5 (2.4 percent) of respondents have the monthly household consumption expenditure of Rs. 10001-15000, 3 (1.5 percent) of respondents have the monthly household consumption expenditure of Rs. 15001-20,000.

In Varanasi district out of 200 respondents, 94 (47 percent) of respondents have the monthly household consumption expenditure of Rs. 5001-7500, 72 (36 percent) of respondents have the monthly household

consumption expenditure of Rs. 7501-10000, 23 (11.5 percent) of respondents have the monthly household consumption expenditure of Rs. 10001-15,000, 7 (3.5 percent) of respondents have the monthly household consumption expenditure of Rs. 2500-5000, 4 (2 percent) of respondents have the monthly household consumption expenditure of Rs. 15001-20,000.

It concluded that majority of respondents in both districts, 56.8 % have monthly household consumption expenditure on food and non-food items of Rs. 5000-7500, followed by 24.4 % respondents have expenditures between the range of 7501- 10000 and 10.1 % of respondents have expenditure in the range of Rs. 2500-5000.

Table: 14 Distribution of Respondents by Type of Ration Card

Districts/Type of Ration Card	BPL Card	APL Card	AAY Card	No Card	Total
Azamgarh	85 (41.5)	110 (53.7)	7 (3.4)	3 (1.5)	205 (100.0)
Akbarpur	13 (37.1)	20 (57.1)	2 (5.7)	0 (0.0)	35 (100.0)
Atraulia	8 (20.0)	32 (80.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	40 (100.0)
Jahanaganj	13 (40.6)	16 (50.0)	3 (9.4)	0 (0.0)	32 (100.0)
Jeeyanpur	12 (42.9)	14 (50.0)	2 (7.1)	0 (0.0)	28 (100.0)
Mubarakpur	39 (55.7)	28 (40.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (4.3)	70 (100.0)
Varanasi	53 (26.5)	125 (62.5)	0 (0.0)	22 (11.0)	200 (100.0)
Bajardiha	20 (33.3)	32 (53.3)	0 (0.0)	8 (13.3)	60 (100.0)
Jaitpura	17 (34.0)	24 (48.0)	0 (0.0)	9 (18.0)	50 (100.0)
Jalalipura	4 (13.3)	26 (86.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	30 (100.0)
Lohta	7 (23.3)	21 (70.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (6.7)	30 (100.0)
Madanpura	5 (16.7)	22 (73.3)	0 (0.0)	3 (10.0)	30 (100.0)
Grand Total	138 (34.1)	235 (58.0)	7 (1.7)	25 (6.2)	405 (100.0)

Source: Compiled from collected data

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

In Azamgarh district, more than half of the respondents own APL (Above Poverty Line) cards and it shows the social status of the respondents. Out of 205 respondents 110 (53.7 percent) of respondents have APL cards, 85 (41.5 percent) respondents have BPL Card, 7 (3.4 percent) respondents have AAY cards and 3 (1.5 percent) respondents are living without ration cards.

The same inclination was reported in Varanasi district, out of 200 respondents 125 (62.5 percent) respondents have APL cards, 22 (11 percent) respondents are living without ration cards and 53 (26.5 percent) respondents have BPL cards.

It is found that majority of respondents (58 percent) have APL card while 34.1 percent and 1.7 percent

respondents have BPL card and AAY card respectively. It is also observed that most of the BPL and AAY cards belong to SCs/STs social groups.

Table: 15 Purpose of Loan:

Districts/Purpose of Loan	Weaving	Other purposes	Both	Total
Azamgarh	54	144	7	205
	(26.3)	(70.2)	(3.4)	(100)
Akbarpur	8	27	0	35
	(22.9)	(77.1)	(0.0)	(100)
Atraulia	18	18	4	40
	(45.0)	(45.0)	(10.0)	(100)
Jahanaganj	6	26	0	32
	(18.8)	(81.3)	(0.0)	(100)
Jeeyanpur	9	19	0	28
	(32.1)	(67.9)	(0.0)	(100)
Mubarakpur	13	54	3	70
	(18.6)	(77.1)	(4.3)	(100)
Varanasi	81	101	18	200
	(40.5)	(50.5)	(9.0)	(100)
Bajardiha	16	41	3	60
	(26.7)	(68.3)	(5.0)	(100)
Jaitpura	23	23	4	50
	(46.0)	(46.0)	(8.0)	(100)
Jalalipura	14	11	5	30
	(46.7)	(36.7)	(16.7)	(100)
Lohta	13	15	2	30
	(43.3)	(50.0)	(6.7)	(100)
Madanpura	15	11	4	30
	(50.0)	(36.7)	(13.3)	(100)
Grand Total	135	245	25	405
	(33.3)	(60.5)	(6.2)	(100)

Source: Compiled from collected data.

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

The table: 15 shows purpose of loan/debt taken by the sample respondents. In Azamgarh district it can be observed that 70.2 percent of total respondents were borrowed money for other purposes and 26.3 percent of respondents were borrowed for weaving purposes.

In Varanasi district, 50.5 percent of the respondent were borrowed money for other purposes and 40.5 percent of respondents were borrowed for weaving purposes.

It can be found that majority (60.5 percent) of respondents were borrowed money for other purposes and 33.3 percent of respondents were borrowing for weaving purposes. The other purposes are home needs, children education and marriages and to fulfil these purposes they were pushed off in to the indebtedness.

It can be found that majority (60.5 percent) of respondents were borrowed money for other purposes and 33.3 percent of respondents were borrowing for weaving purposes. The other purposes are home needs, children education and marriages and to fulfil these purposes they were pushed off in to the indebtedness.

Table: 16 Source of Loan

Districts/Source of Loan	Money Lender	Master Weaver/Gaddidar	Friends/Relatives	Cooperative-Society	Commercial Banks	SHGs	Total
Azamgarh	40 (19.5)	64 (31.2)	30 (14.6)	26 (12.7)	32 (15.6)	13 (6.3)	205 (100)
Akbarpur	6 (17.1)	12 (34.3)	7 (20.0)	4 (11.4)	5 (14.3)	1 (2.9)	35 (100)
Atraulia	7 (17.5)	8 (20.0)	6 (15.0)	3 (7.5)	10 (25.0)	6 (15.0)	40 (100)
Jahanaganj	5 (15.6)	11 (34.4)	5 (15.6)	6 (18.8)	4 (12.5)	1 (3.1)	32 (100)
Jeeyanpur	7 (25.0)	9 (32.1)	3 (10.7)	6 (21.4)	2 (7.1)	1 (3.6)	28 (100)
Mubarakpur	15	24	9	7	11	4	70
Varanasi	51 (25.5)	75 (37.5)	22 (11.0)	18 (9.0)	21 (10.5)	13 (6.5)	200 (100)
Bajardiha	14 (23.3)	20 (33.3)	6 (10.0)	7 (11.7)	9 (15.0)	4 (6.7)	60 (100)
Jaitpura	13 (26.0)	20 (40.0)	7 (14.0)	2 (4.0)	4 (8.0)	4 (8.0)	50 (100)
Jalalipura	8 (26.7)	7 (23.3)	4 (13.3)	3 (10.0)	5 (16.7)	3 (10.0)	30 (100)
Lohta	10 (33.3)	14 (46.7)	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	1 (3.3)	1 (3.3)	30 (100)
Madanpura	6 (20.0)	14 (46.7)	3 (10.0)	4 (13.3)	2 (6.7)	1 (3.3)	30 (100)
Grand Total	91 (22.5)	139 (34.3)	52 (12.8)	44 (10.9)	53 (13.1)	26 (6.4)	405 (100)

Source: Compiled from collected data.

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

In Azamgarh district, out of 205 respondents, 64 (31.2 percent) respondents are depending on master weavers, 40 (19.5 percent) respondents are getting loan from money lenders, 32 (15.6 percent) respondents are getting from commercial banks, 30 (14.6 percent) respondents depending on friends and relatives, 26 (12.7 percent) respondents are depending on banks for indebtedness, 26 (12.7 percent) respondents are depending on cooperative societies for indebtedness and rest 13 respondents (6.3 percent) are taken from SHGs.

In Varanasi district, out of 200 respondents, 75 (37.5 percent) respondents are depending on master weavers, 51 (25.5 percent) respondents are getting loan from money lenders, 21 (10.5 percent) respondents are getting from commercial banks, 22 (11 percent) respondents depending on friends and relatives, 21 (10.5 percent) respondents are depending on banks for indebtedness and 9 (18 percent) respondents are depending on cooperative societies

for indebtedness and rest 13 respondents (6.5 percent) are taken from SHGs.

It can be found that majority of the respondents (34.3 percent) are depending on master weavers and 22.5 percent of respondents are getting loan from money lenders.

The handloom weavers depend very much on the master weavers, the master weavers have learnt to put up with these problems as they have taken loan from them. Master weavers establish long term economic relationship with weavers by giving large sums as an advance and personal interest free loans which are deducted as small amounts from weavers wage. Money lender is also very important source of loan to handloom weavers and he exploited the weavers by charging high interest rates. Banks and cooperative societies are very insignificant source for credit.

Table: 17 Type of employment Status

Districts/Employment Status	Independent Weaver	Under Master Weaver	Under Cooperative Society	Master Weaver	Total
Azamgarh	38	146	12	9	205
	(18.5)	(71.2)	(5.9)	(4.4)	(100.0)
Akbarpur	4	29	0	2	35
	(11.4)	(82.9)	(0.0)	(5.7)	(100.0)
Atraulia	5	33	0	2	40
	(12.5)	(82.5)	(0.0)	(5.0)	(100.0)
Jahanaganj	7	25	0	0	32
	(21.9)	(78.1)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(100.0)
Jecyanpur	11	15	0	2	28
	(39.3)	(53.6)	(0.0)	(7.1)	(100.0)
Mubarakpur	11	44	12	3	70
	(15.7)	(62.9)	(17.1)	(4.3)	(100.0)
Varanasi	52	126	11	11	200
	(26.0)	(63.0)	(5.5)	(5.5)	(100.0)
Bajardiha	15	38	4	3	60
	(25.0)	(63.3)	(6.7)	(5.0)	(100.0)
Jaitpura	17	30	1	2	50
	(34.0)	(60.0)	(2.0)	(4.0)	(100.0)
Jalalipura	7	20	0	3	30
	(23.3)	(66.7)	(0.0)	(10.0)	(100.0)
Lohta	6	20	3	1	30
	(20.0)	(66.7)	(10.0)	(3.3)	(100.0)
Madanpura	7	18	3	2	30
	(23.3)	(60.0)	(10.0)	(6.7)	(100.0)
Grand Total	90	272	23	20	405
	(22.2)	(67.2)	(5.7)	(4.9)	(100.0)

Source: Compiled from collected data.

Note: Figures in parentheses is percentage of the respondents

In Azamgarh district, out of 205 respondents, 146 (71.2 percent) respondents are working under master weaver, 52 respondents (18.5 percent) working as Independent weavers, 12 respondents (5.9 percent) are working under cooperative societies and 4 respondents (4.4 percent) are master weavers.

In Varanasi district, out of 200 respondents, 126 (63 percent) respondents are working under master weaver, 52 respondents (26 percent) are working as independent weavers, 11 respondents (5.5 percent) are working under cooperative societies and 11 respondents (5.5 percent) working as master weavers. It is found that majority of handloom weavers in both districts which is 67.2 percent working under master

weavers. It is also found that 22.2 percent weavers are working as independent, 5.7 percent weavers are working under cooperative societies and 4.9 percent working as master weavers.

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

This paper has examined the socio-economic conditions of the handloom weavers. It found that most of the respondents (36.8 %) were between 36-45 years of age. The age group of the handloom weavers in the Varanasi and Azamgarh districts shows that the number of respondents up to 25 years of age is low. The younger generation is not opting for weaving as their preferred profession. It found that nearly 91 per cent of weavers were male, while only 9 per cent were female. It observed that the female members of their family assist male handloom weavers. Therefore, in the study area, male handloom weavers are directly employed towards handloom weaving rather than female members. The majority (65 per cent) of weavers belonged to the Muslim religion, and (35 per cent) of the weavers were from the Hindu religion. Most of the respondents, i.e. 73.1 per cent, belonged to OBCs social group, whereas 19.8 per cent of respondents were from SCs social group. In both districts, the higher percentage of weavers are married (84.4 per cent), followed by unmarried (10.9 per cent), widowed or widower (4.2 per cent) and divorced or separated (0.5 per cent). The majority of the respondents (56.5%) have a joint family, and 43.5% of respondents have a nuclear family. The majority of respondents (60.5 per cent) live in pucca houses, and the rest, 27.2 per cent and 12.3 per cent, live in semi-pucca, and kutcha houses, respectively and 90 per cent were the owners of their house, and the rest 10 per cent lived in rented homes. The majority of respondents (28.6 per cent) were a primary level of education, about 28.1 per cent respondents had below the primary level of education, and 24.7 per cent of respondents had never attended school. It observed that less educated respondents opt for handloom weaving more significantly because handloom weavers prefer their traditional occupation

immediately rather than qualifying further. The study shows that most of the respondents, i.e. 81.7 per cent, have a weaving background. The majority of respondents (40.2 per cent) have eyesight problems, (21.5 per cent) of respondents suffer from back pain, (19.8 per cent) of respondents have the problem of joint pain, and (17.3 per cent) of respondents have the problem of hearing. The majority of the respondents (63.2 per cent) in both districts have a monthly household income between Rs. 5001 to 7500. Finally, the respondents in the Varanasi district have a monthly household income better than those in the Azamgarh district because the designs made by the Varanasi weavers are relatively innovative (particularly jacquard) and with modern technology. It concluded that the majority of respondents in both districts, 56.8 % have monthly household consumption expenditure on food and non-food items of Rs. 5000-7500. Most respondents (58 per cent) have APL cards, while 34.1 per cent and 1.7 per cent have BPL cards and AAY cards, respectively. Most BPL and AAY cards belong to SCs/STs social groups. The majority, 60.5 per cent, of respondents borrowed money for other purposes, and 33.3 per cent of respondents borrowed it for weaving purposes. The different purposes are home needs, children's education and marriages, and to fulfil these purposes, they pushed off into indebtedness. The majority of handloom weavers in both districts, 67.2 per cent, work under master weavers. The study found that 34.3 per cent of weavers depend on master weavers, and 22.5 per cent of weavers are getting loans from money lenders.

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